

Correlated multistate model for the progression of chronic kidney disease with detecting risk factors effect

Modelo multiestado correlacionado para la progresión de la enfermedad renal crónica con detección del efecto de los factores de riesgo

247

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Abstract

AIM: This study examined a multistate model with correlated frailty between CKD transitions by fitting a model with a bivariate gamma distribution.

Methodology: By incorporating as a frailty term, correlated multistate modeling was able to account for the dependence between moderate and severe CKD in an analysis of kidney dysfunction progression data from 153 patients. Therefore, frailty and correlated-frailty multistate models were used to evaluate the role that significant prognostic factors play in disease progression.

Results: Hypertension and diabetes have a threefold and fourfold increased risk of progressing from state mild to moderate CKD in both models respectively, covid-19 has a significant risk of transitioning from mild to moderate and severe CKD state in both models.

Conclusion: The underlying dynamics of CKD can be better understood with the help of multistate models, which do this by analyzing the subjects' entire event histories. Under the hypothesis of a positive correlation between the frailties for the two exits from mild CKD, this evidence supports the superiority of a model fit with a bivariate gamma distribution.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), Multi-State Model, Frailty, Bivariate gamma distribution

Resumen

Objetivo: Este estudio examinó un modelo multiestado con fragilidad correlacionada entre transiciones de ERC ajustando un modelo con una distribución gamma bivalente.

Metodología: Mediante la incorporación como término de fragilidad, el modelado multiestado correlacionado fue capaz de dar cuenta de la dependencia entre la ERC moderada y grave en un análisis de datos de progresión de la disfunción renal de 153 pacientes. Por lo tanto, se utilizaron los modelos frailty y multiestado correlacionado-frailty para evaluar el papel que juegan los factores pronósticos significativos en la progresión de la enfermedad.

Resultados: La hipertensión y la diabetes triplican y cuadruplican el riesgo de progresión del estado leve a moderado de ERC en ambos modelos respectivamente, el covid-19 tiene un riesgo significativo de transición del estado leve a moderado y grave de ERC en ambos modelos.

Conclusiones: La dinámica subyacente de la ERC puede comprenderse mejor con la ayuda de modelos multiestado, que lo hacen analizando el historial completo de eventos de los sujetos.

Bajo la hipótesis de una correlación positiva entre las fragilidades para las dos salidas de la ERC leve, esta evidencia apoya la superioridad de un modelo ajustado con una distribución gamma bivalente.

Palabras clave: Enfermedad Renal Crónica (ERC), Modelo Multi-Estado, Fragilidad, Distribución gamma bivalente

The increasing prevalence of chronic kidney disease has emerged as a critical public health issue. However, if kidney issues are caught early and treated, they can be prevented altogether. Chronic diseases, including kidney disease, can be prevented or their progression slowed with the help of medication and changes in lifestyle. Given the frequency with which patients with renal disease require hospitalization, it stands to reason that their treating physicians would be interested in the insights gleaned from outcomes of modeling such as persistence, longevity, and disease progression in these patients. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) affects a sizable percentage of adult populations in developed nations^{11,24}. Hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease are additional risk factors for chronic kidney disease^{5,11,15,24}. The COVID-19 pandemic had a greater impact on the health, daily functioning, and mental disorder of patients in stages III and IV of chronic kidney disease than on those in stages I and II. More intensive medical and psychological support is required for patients with CKD, especially those with low eGFR²³. CKD is associated with an increased risk of infection and mortality from the COVID-19 virus^{12,20}. COVID-19 infection has been linked to kidney failure symptoms including proteinuria, hematuria, and elevated serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen levels²². Serum creatinine levels are commonly used to diagnose CKD. Serum creatinine levels are inversely proportional to the kidneys' filtration efficiency (glomerular filtration rate; GFR). When compared to a simple survival model, a multi-state model is preferable for the management of diabetes, chronic kidney disease, and other similar conditions^{2,10}. In the fixed-effect multi-state model, the differences in risk that individuals face are explained by the observed explanatory variables. There may be unobserved heterogeneity that affects the risk even after all potential confounders have been considered⁷. For instance, several factors impact survival that were not quantified in the available data. Therefore, some people are more likely to develop moderate or severe disease states under identical covariate values, while other people are more likely to maintain a healthier state. Frailty is the term used to describe the random effect used in survival analysis to model such unobserved effects. In describing the potential dangers of moving across state lines, this research isolates random effects with the assumption of dependency. Two of the most common ways to examine bivariate survival data are the shared frailty model and the correlated frailty model^{8,14}. The correlated frailty model is usually seen as a bigger version of the shared frailty model¹³. According to the correlated frailty model, rather than being shared among members of a group, frailties are correlated. Two different frailties were found in a pair of twins, but these values are

correlated, bivariate correlated frailty model is the name given to this model, The connection between the twins' two frailties was characterized by a correlation coefficient²⁸. For survival data, there are several bivariate frailty models to consider²¹. Both independent and correlated frailty between moderate and severe CKD states were taken into consideration when putting the illness-death model into practice. Investigating the connections between different transition risks in a multistate model is of interest to us. As a result, we talk about the correlated frailty models. In order to a model of frailty between transitions from mild CKD to moderate and severe CKD states and propose a remedy using multi-state and frailty methodologies, this study examined subject event dependency in CKD survival data using a bivariate gamma distribution. Transition times in the joint frailty multistate model were interdependent. Both moderate and severe CKD hazards were jointly modeled in this study. According to the Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative (KDOQI), five stages of chronic kidney disease (CKD) describe progressively worsening kidney function and are considered irreversible¹⁹:

Table 1. Staging of Chronic Kidney Disease

State	Description	eGFR(ml/min/1.73 m2)
I	Normal in eGFR	> 90
II	Mild	60-89
III	Moderate	30-59
IV	Severe	15-29
V	Kidney failure	< 15 (or dialysis)

Source: KDOQI. GRF: Glomerular Filtration Rate

A correlated multi-state with random effects model has proven useful for describing the changes an individual undergoes between states in the presence of continuous time. We have used this model to detect hazards of transitioning from one state to another in light of the relation between states with a term of correlated frailty, which is important for understanding chronic kidney disease, which is irreversible. The kidneys' overall health is symbolized by the chronic kidney disease stage. There are five stages of chronic kidney disease (CKD), each representing a progressively worsening loss of kidney function.

Data Description

Researchers contacted several reputable institutions, including Shar Hospital in the Sulaymaniyah governorate, to obtain access to their CKD patient records. More than 267 patients indicated they were willing to share their data by responding positively. After receiving adequate information, they all agreed. This investigation’s findings were only consistent with 153 patient records. This study looks back at the medical records of 153 people with CKD who were seen between February 2015 and May 2022. The gender, age and BMI of each patient were documented. As well as other aspects of each patient’s medical history, diabetes, blood pressure, the presence or absence of the coronavirus, and the concentrations of creatinine, albumin, and urea were recorded. A physician was present for patient monitoring. Categorical variables such as sex, blood pressure, diabetes mellitus, and covid-19 status are assessed against standards established by the World Health Organization or another internationally recognized organization. The discrete variables are age, body mass index, serum creatinine, urea, and albumin (Alb). If the patient’s blood albumin level is below 4.5 g/dl, their urea level is between 42 and 131 mg/dl, and their serum creatinine level is greater than or equal to 1.4 mg/dl, nephropathy can be diagnosed. Organization of data is essential for fitting multistate models. The assigned ID numbers make it easy to categorize subjects. Therefore, extra care should be taken during data collection to ensure that all patient-specific information is recorded under the same identifier. The example data set’s data format is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Multiple-state model example data structure.

Patient Identifier	Age	Time	Sex	State	Hypertension	Diabetes	Covid-19
41	40.11	0	1	2	1	0	0
41	42.16	2.06	1	2	1	0	0
41	44.14	4.04	1	2	1	0	0
41	46.14	6.04	1	2	1	0	0
77	38.76	0	0	1	0	1	1
77	40.77	2.01	0	1	0	1	1
77	42.79	4.03	0	1	0	1	1
145	52.43	0	0	1	0	1	0
145	54.43	2	0	1	0	1	0
145	56.49	4.06	0	1	0	1	0

Source: by researcher.

A state transition and its associated probability are terms used in the context of scientific inquiry. Chronic kidney disease progresses through five stages, from I to V. The first four are only passing phases, but phase five is where things get exciting. The frailty is defined for transition II → III and II → IV. A patient may continuously only make forward transitions between discrete temporary states.

Figure 1. State Transition Diagram. Source: by researcher

Multi-State Model

Since the development of a disease typically involves several transitions between states, multi-state models based on the Markov process are frequently used to simulate the course of the disease over an indefinite period. [9] We proposed a five-state multi-state Markov model of renal disease progression based on the available data. The frailty is defined for transition II → III and II → IV. Markovian processes are those in which the future can be predicted only from the present. The model is shown in Figure 1. Despite this, CKD always moves forward through its stages. Because the rate of disease progression is a continuous function of time and the transition probability between states varies over time, we have considered a Markov process-based continuous time multistate model⁶. If $S(t) = i$ represents the patient’s current state, then the rate at which the patient transitions between states during the interval $(t + \Delta t)$ can be expressed as:

$$\lambda_{ij}(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(X_{t+\Delta t} = j | X_t = i)}{\Delta t}$$

λ_{ij} represents the risk of transitioning from state i to state j . Using a proportional hazards regression model, the influence of covariates on the severity of transitions was accounted for. Assuming the covariance matrix x , $\lambda_{ij}[t|X(t)] = \lambda_{ij0} \exp[B_{ij}^T X(t)]$

The regression coefficients, denoted by the vector B_{ij} , In our prior study, we discovered fixed effects on transitions for CKD progression on the same data set²⁶. This study talks about random effects when considering the risks of moving between states especially mild CKD states to moderate and severe CKD states independently and jointly.

Frailty multi-state model

The hazard function for individual b in transition (i, j) according to the frailty model is given by

$$\lambda_{i,j,b}(t|W_{ij,b}, x, b) = \lambda_{ij,0}(t) \exp(\beta_{ij}^T x) W_{ij,b}$$

where x represents the vector of fixed-effect covariates, β_{ij} the vector of parameters, and $\lambda_{ij,0}(t)$ the initial hazard. Assuming a positive hazard function necessitates a positive frailty, denoted by $w_{ij,b}$. The gamma distribution is frequently applied to describe frailty. Gamma-distributed frailty W has the following probability density

$$f(w) = \frac{\gamma^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} w^{\alpha-1} e^{-\gamma w}$$

shape parameter = $\alpha > 0$, rate parameter = $\gamma > 0$,

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} / \exp(t) dt$$

$$E(W) = \frac{\alpha}{\gamma}, \text{Var}(W) = \frac{\alpha}{\gamma^2}$$

$W_{ij,b} \sim \Gamma(d)$, where shape parameter = rate parameter = d . So, probability density of $w_{ij,b}$ is given by

$$f(w_{ij,b}) = \frac{d^d}{\Gamma(d)} w_{ij,b}^{d-1} e^{-dw_{ij,b}}$$

$$\text{where } E(W_{ij,b}) = 1, \text{Var}(W_{ij,b}) = \frac{1}{d}.$$

for individual b with an absorbing state, the frailty model's likelihood contribution is provided by:

$$\begin{aligned} L_b(\theta|b, y, x) &= P(Y_2 = y_2, \dots, Y_M = y_M | Y_1 = y_1, \theta, x) \\ &= \int_{\Omega_{w_b}} \prod_{m=2}^M P(Y_m = y_m | Y_{m-1} = y_{m-1}, \theta, x, w_b) S(y_m | y_{m-1}, \theta, x, w_b) \\ &\quad * f(w_b | \theta) dw_b, \end{aligned}$$

where θ is the vector of all model parameters, $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_M)$ are the states observed at time t , and t is the observed variable in the intervals t_1, t_2, \dots, t_M , frailty is denoted by w_b , and the parameter space of w_b is denoted by Ω_{w_b} . Assuming individual independence, for N people, we can write down the likelihood function as:

$$L(\theta|y, x) = \prod_{b=1}^N L_b(\theta|b, y, x).$$

To learn more about the correlation between two transitions in the multi-state model, we will use the Cheriyan bivariate gamma distribution to fit a frailty model. The bivariate frailty distribution is an extension of the frailty model that describes frailties in terms of two transition hazards, Cheriyan derived a bivariate gamma using the reduction method^{16,18,27}. For a person b who moves from state i to state j and from state p to state q , for instance:

$$\lambda_{i,j,b}(t|x, W_{ij,b}) = \lambda_{ij,0}(t) \exp(\beta_{ij}^T x) W_{ij,b}$$

$$\lambda_{p,q,b}(t|x, W_{pq,b}) = \lambda_{pq,0}(t) \exp(\beta_{pq}^T x) W_{pq,b}$$

Where $W_{ij,b}$ and $W_{pq,b}$ have a bivariate distribution that may be either correlated or uncorrelated. One can

think of bivariate gamma distributions as a more general form of the one-variable gamma distribution.

Let $Z_l \sim \Gamma(\alpha_l), l = 0, 1, 2$, be three independent random variables, where $W_l = Z_0 + Z_l, l = 0, 1, 2$. As a result, the expression for the bivariate gamma density is²⁷:

$$f(W_{ij,b}, W_{pq,b}) = \frac{\gamma^{\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2} e^{-\gamma(W_{ij,b} + W_{pq,b})}}{\Gamma(\alpha_0)\Gamma(\alpha_1)\Gamma(\alpha_2)} \int_0^{\min(W_{ij,b}, W_{pq,b})} z_0^{\alpha_0-1} (W_{ij,b} - z_0)^{\alpha_1-1} (W_{pq,b} - z_0)^{\alpha_2-1} e^{-\gamma z_0} dz_0$$

$$w_1, w_2 \geq z_0 \geq 0, \text{ and } \alpha_l \geq 0, l = 0, 1, 2.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since } E(W_{ij,b}) &= \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_1}{\gamma} = 1, E(W_{pq,b}) = \frac{\alpha_0 + \alpha_2}{\gamma} = 1 \\ \text{Var}(W_1) &= \text{Var}(W_1) = \frac{(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1)}{(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1)^2} \end{aligned} \quad \text{we obtain that } \alpha_1 = \alpha_2, \gamma = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1$$

Therefore, frailties $W_{ij,b}$ and $W_{pq,b}$ conform to a gamma distribution at the margin

$$W_{ij,b} \sim \Gamma(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1, \alpha_0 + \alpha_1), W_{pq,b} \sim \Gamma(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1, \alpha_0 + \alpha_1),$$

$$\rho w = \frac{\text{Cov}(W_{ij,b}, W_{pq,b})}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(W_{ij,b})\text{Var}(W_{pq,b})}} = \frac{\alpha_0}{\alpha_0 + \alpha_1} > 0.$$

If the transition hazards are positively correlated, then this approach can be used to add frailties.

Given below is the likelihood contribution for the frailty model for individual b .

$$\begin{aligned} L_b(\theta|b, y, x) &= P(Y_m = y_m | Y_{m-1} = y_{m-1}, \theta, x) \\ &= \int_{\Omega_{w_b}} \prod_{m=2}^M P(Y_m = y_m | Y_{m-1} = y_{m-1}, \theta, x, w_b) f(w_b | \theta) dw_b, \end{aligned}$$

where $y = (y_m, y_{m-1})$ are the observable states at the observable times $t_m, w_b = (W_{ij,b}, W_{pq,b})$ denotes random effects for individual b for 2-dimensional frailty models. Our goal is to model chronic kidney disease (CKD) progression, so we consider two frailty modeling strategies: (1) defining frailty independently for CKD transition II \rightarrow III and II \rightarrow IV (Univariate one parameter gamma distributed frailty model) and (2) defining correlated frailty for CKD transition II \rightarrow III and II \rightarrow IV (Bivariate gamma distributed frailty model). because we want to learn more about what happens during the gradual escalation from a mild CKD state to a moderate and severe one.

$$\lambda_{24} = \exp(\beta_{24,0} + \beta_{24} \text{Gender} + \beta_{24} \text{HTN} + \beta_{24} \text{Diabetes} + \beta_{24} \text{Covid} \sim 19)$$

Where $\beta_{23,0}$ and $\beta_{24,0}$ are the intercept.

2.4. Model selection

Since different covariates and frailties in various transition hazards can be defined in the analysis of multi-state models, Models must be compared and the best one chosen. Two practical techniques for model comparison are introduced in the section that follows.

To find the model that best fits the data, we use AIC to compare the alternatives.; [1]

$$AIC = -2 \log(\hat{L}) + 2k,$$

Where; L = maximum likelihood function, k = No. of independent regression variables.

If you're looking for an alternate way to evaluate the models, try the Bayesian information criterion²⁵. This is provided by

$$BIC = -2 \log(\hat{L}) + \log(n)k,$$

where n is the number of observations, L is the maximum of the likelihood function, and k is the number of free parameters in the regression analysis (including the intercept).

Results

Table 3 shows that of the total number of patients, 153 (90 men and 63 women), Patients' average (SD) ages were 47.53 (12.83) years. The mean (SD) values for BMI, creatinine, urea, and albumin were 25.84 (5.83), 2.70 (1.36), 98.08 (3.36), and 3.45 (0.64), respectively. A total of 42 patients (41.83%) were diagnosed with hypertension, 75 were diagnosed with diabetes (49.02%), and 49 were given Covid-19 (32.03%).

Table 3. Statistics of the Demographic and Clinical Features.

Variables	n (%) or mean (SD)
Age (SD)	47.53(12.83)
BMI(SD)	25.84(5.83)
Urea(SD)	98.08(33.4)
Cr(SD)	2.7(1.36)
Alb(SD)	3.45(0.64)
Sex-male(%)	90(58.82)
Diabetic-yes(%)	75(49.02)
Hypertension-yes(%)	64(41.83)
Covid-19-yes(%)	49(32.03)

Utilizing Frequency (%) for categorical data and Mean (SD) for continuous data

The first state had 67 patients, followed by 21 in the second, 26 in the third, and 39 in the fourth. Change in CKD patients' states between visits are shown in Table 4. The severity of chronic kidney disease is proportional to how often a patient has routine checkups. Patients in Stage I remained in that category after 346 visits. From the previous levels, 2, 4, 10, and 18 patients have advanced to Stage V. A high percentage of patients with CKD stage IV advance to CKD Stage V. The percentage of patients whose health remained stable between measurements is represented by the diagonal. The estimated statistical probability of surviving Figure 2 shows the resulting graph.

Table 4. Transition synopsis.

From	To				
	I	IV	III	IV	V
I	346	82	37	12	2
II	0	121	47	30	4
III	0	0	74	35	10
IV	0	0	0	31	18

Figure 2. Fitted Survival Probability Plot.

For those with severe CKD, the chance of survival over 10 years is approximately 0.1, while those with moderate CKD have 0.4, those with mild CKD have 0.5, and those with normal CKD have 0.7. Within the first five years of developing severe CKD, the patient's life expectancy plummets to approximately 0.3 years.

Table 5. Hazard Ratio and 95% Confidence Interval with incorporating independent frailty terms

	Mild to Moderate transition	Mild to Severe transition
	Exp β (CI 95%)	Exp β (CI 95%)
Sex-male	1.56(0.6-1.92)	0.86(0.29-1.47)
Hypertension-yes	3.16(1.92-3.94)*	1.69(0.36-3.02)
Diabetic-yes	3.31(1.53-4.12)*	2.23(1.44-4.16)
Covid-yes	2.19(0.97-5.47)	2.99(1.91-5.84)*
The variance of the frailty	1.23 (0.98-1.77)*	0.56 (0.28-0.76)*
$-2\log(\hat{L})$	1622.46	1626.63
AIC	1634.46	1638.63
BIC	1635.57	1639.74

*: values are significant.

The outcomes of the standalone frailty model are displayed in Table 5. Hypertension was identified as a risk factor, and its impact on the transition from mild CKD state to moderate CKD state was found to be substantial [HR_{23} : 3.16(1.92-3.94)] using this model, which took into account individual characteristics. There was a significant difference in improvement rates between patients with and without diabetes, with patients with diabetes having a higher risk of complications [HR_{23} : 3.31(1.53-4.12)]. Covid-19 was a significant risk factor in the progression from mild to severe symptoms [HR_{24} : 2.99(1.91-5.84)]. This demonstrates that patients with covid-19 face a high mortality rate. $d_{23} = 0.81$ and $d_{24} = 1.79$ are the frailty parameters.

Table 6. Hazard Ratio and 95% Confidence Interval with incorporating correlated frailty terms

	Mild to Moderate transition	Mild to Severe transition
	Exp β (CI 95%)	Exp β (CI 95%)
Sex-male	1.55(0.64-1.98)	1.94(0.71-3.23)
Hypertention-yes	3.9(2.01-4.61)*	1.05(0.65-1.23)
Diabetic-yes	4.31(2.9-5.14)*	1.82 (1.27-3.23)
Covid-yes	2.36(1.06-4.47)*	4.41(2.54-6.23)*
The variance of the frailty	0.33(0.12-0.93)	
$-2\log(\hat{L})$	1608.32	
AIC	1628.32	
BIC	1630.17	

*: values are significant.

According to joint frailty results (Table 6), there was an association between the transition of mild to moderate CKD (II \rightarrow III) and the following severe CKD (II \rightarrow IV). $\hat{\alpha}_0 = 1.12$ and $\hat{\alpha}_1 = 1.94$ are the parameters for bivariate gamma distribution. Bivariate frailties W_1 and $W_2 \sim \Gamma(3.06, 3.06)$, and the correlation coefficient is $\hat{\rho} = 0.37$. This showed that the incidence of moderate CKD was positively associated with severe CKD. HTN, Diabetic, and Covid-19 significantly affected Moderate and severe CKD states in this model. In addition, the $2\log(L)$, AIC, and BIC criteria were proposed to select the correlated frailty model as the model that best fits the data. The correlated frailty model was chosen due to its lower $2\log(L)$, AIC, and BIC values, which demonstrated a superior model in this regard.

If we know how chronic diseases progress, Disease burden projections allow us to assess the efficacy and cost-effectiveness of potential interventions. Since Markov chain models can describe an individual's time evolution across multiple states, they are frequently used in studies of chronic disease. Disease progression rates and the factors that influence them can be accurately modeled with the help of simulations. The incidence of CKD is higher in men than in women. Both diabetes and high blood pressure play a major role in the progression of CKD. Multi-state models based on Markov chains are frequently used for modeling and analyzing CKD progression³. The model is an effective tool for study because it can explain why certain side effects occur in patients receiving a particular treatment. A multi-state model is superior to a basic survival model for the management of chronic renal disease and other disorders². For the multistate model to work, the following components are required: Figure 1 and Table 1 show the possible stages and transitions for this procedure. Modify the model using the appropriate program, and then analyze the data. Challenges in this study include the current study does not include some participants because they did not respond positively or refused to provide their data. Our results may not generalize to other populations, as the original study population was skewed toward Whites. The numbers were crunched using R 4.2.2's MSM package and Frailty Pack^{17,32}. Incorporating individual heterogeneity into our illness-death model allowed us to both capture and exert some degree of control over previously unobserved heterogeneity in this study. The correlated frailty MSM framework reveals the interconnected nature of transition intensities. By using this model, we were able to remove the estimator's bias and produce more accurate projections. In the typical survival model, the gamma distribution is frequently used to represent frailty. From both an analytical and a computational perspective, it is a very useful distribution⁴. The results of the analysis demonstrate that a bivariate gamma distribution can provide a good model fit under the assumption of a positive correlation between the frailties for the two exits from mild CKD. Both hypertension and diabetes were found to be strong indicators of future CKD development and progression, especially from mild CKD to moderate and severe CKD. It appears that CKD is linked to severe cases of COVID-19 infection. Patients with CKD should therefore take additional precautions to avoid contracting the infection. Close observation is warranted for any CKD patient for whom COVID-19 is suspected.

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